

Colonial Modernity and its Offsprings: An Inquiry into the Cultural Sphere of Nineteenth Century Bengal

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Abstract

Nineteenth Century is a time of seismic shift in both the political and cultural domain across India. Among other provinces Bengal received a substantial amount of attention from colonial rulers. Consequently, Bengal witnessed a surge in emulating the western parameters in their cultural sphere which gradually made its way into the political awakening of the subjects as well. Bengal, especially Kolkata, as a centre of colonial governance found itself at the centre of a vortex of cultural exchanges—rise of positivist philosophy, establishment of civil societies, print capitalism which helped to pave the way for a modernity that was initially an European import. However, it may be considered that with time the educated Bengali middle class appropriated the parameters of modernity and carved out their own version(s) of it. This modernity left its indelible mark on cultural and religious practise across Bengal. This paper would seek to look at the nature of this appropriation and the various scopes this modernity presented the stakeholders of the burgeoning public sphere.

Key words: Nineteenth Century, Bengali Intelligentsia, Modernity, literature, religious reformation, Bengal renaissance.

Modernity is a term marked by a sense of departure— from traditional towards the espousal of new emerging order. However, at the same time it is also a relative temporal frame marked by shifts in both modes of production and ideological choices. A similar kind of seismic shift was also immanent in nineteenth century Bengal as it was standing on the threshold of a modernity which was a by-product of the colonial rule. By 1735 Calcutta had transformed into a powerful centre of trade and was receiving a fair amount of attention from British East India Company. Consequently, the economic and cultural factors joined forces to create a public sphere that was to usher in possibly the most important offshoot of the colonial modernity- Bengal renaissance. Therefore, any inquiry into the nature of the colonial modernity that shaped the nineteenth century Bengali identity, has to take into consideration the functions of various economic as well as social organizations which enormously contributed into making this shift possible.

A cultural phenomenon as multifarious as nineteenth century Bengal has naturally drawn enormous amount of critical interest from the beginning of the past century. More recent works have increasingly been centred around questioning the complex process of involvement of both the colonial masters and their subject in this process. For example, Veena Naregal presents a very complex argument on the nature of rise of the vernacular and its role in building the cultural sphere (Naregal 39). Naregal observes that there was considerable colonial interest in furthering the cause of the vernacular (43). In a certain way it is a different take on Partha Chattopadhyay's theory on how the colonized elite was carefully nurtured and educated to perform their limited role in this colonial space (Chattopadhyay 11). Rosinka Chaudhuri's book *The Literary Thing* engages with the emergence of literary history as discipline in the nineteenth century Bengal and how this new literary tradition

made its presence felt in the public sphere through a detailed discussion on a selection of writers from the nineteenth century (Chaudhuri xxxiii). The present paper is deeply indebted to and influenced by the works mentioned here. However, keeping these arguments in mind, this paper would seek to look closely at the nature of the burgeoning cultural sphere and its reaction to the various components of colonial modernity and how the stakeholders of the very cultural sphere shaped and reshaped the modernity according to their own requirements.

According to the Charter Act of 1813, East India Company was ordered to spend an annual sum of one lac rupees to ensure “the revival and improvement of literature and the encouragement of the learned natives of India...” (qtd. in Bandyopadhyay 13). However, by the time East India Company could act according to the order, Serampore Baptist Mission had already established Serampore Mission Press (1800). Eminent literary historian Sisir Kumar Das marks this printing press as one of the instrumental tropes of the transmission as prose would soon become the main vehicle of literature replacing an old poetical world which many historians started recognizing as the medieval period of Bengali Literature (S K Das 106-107). Much before 1835 (the year Macaulay’s (in)famous minute on education was accepted) or even 1817 (the year Hindu College was established), missionaries started taking initiatives to spread mass education. Sajanikanta Das, in his precise history of Bengali prose (*Bangla Sahityer Itihas*) points out that it was with the publication of *Samachar Darpan* and *Friend of India*, Bengali prose took its first steps towards becoming a major vehicle of literary modernity (Das 3). Along with the printing press, a boarding school was also established in 1800 and by 1820 Serampore mission succeeded in opening a school for girls. Generations of missionaries from Robert May to Felix Carey¹ contributed considerably towards the growth of mass education. Much like Das, another eminent Bengali critic Bhabatosh Dutta also unequivocally endorses the role of Serampore Baptist Mission in spreading mass education and identifies this as the first step towards modernity (Basu 93). Significantly enough, as these schools went up in numbers, there was a sharp fall in the numbers of *Sanskrit Toles*² which were representatives of an older order.

The body of critical literature on nineteenth century has reached a consensus that the modernity in India cannot be perceived without the colonial intervention either missionary or judiciary. As mentioned earlier, critics like Sisir Kumar Das recommend that Serampore Mission Press and Fort William College (1800) went hand in hand in printing and disseminating Bengali text books (qtd. in Basu 97). At the same time, European scholars like William Carey and Henry Derozio started teaching at Fort William College and Hindu College respectively. Therefore, many of the students attending Hindu College (most of whom came from Bengali middle-class families) came in close contact with them (especially Derozio) and were heavily influenced by their ideals. The group called Young Bengal formed around Derozio were famous for their revolutionary zeal. The constellation of the Hindoo college circle, that rose to prominence with Derozio at its centre, spearheaded this initiation into the new consciousness. Much of historical scholarship on this issue has identified this consciousness as a direct result of an acquaintance with westerns humanist ideal. Benoy Ghosh in his book – *Banglar Bidwatsamaj*, gives us an account of how books by Voltaire, Hume, Lock and Rousseau were imported to the Calcutta port and merchants used to put up advertisements of these books amongst other merchandises. These advertisements were regularly published in *Calcutta Chronicle*, *Calcutta Gazette*, *Morning Post*. This awakening had created a stir and a point of considerable concern for both traditionalist Hindus and staunch Christians. Benoy Ghosh records a spiteful commentary by Scottish missionary Alexander Duff on the sudden increase in the circulation of Thomas Paine’s *Age of Reason* and other writings:

Their great authorities...were Hume’s Essays and Paine’s Age of Reason. With copies of the latter, in particular, they were abundantly supplied...It was some wretched bookseller in the United States of America who – basely taking advantage of the reported infidel learnings of a new race of men in the East and apparently regarding no God but his silver dollars, despatched to Calcutta a cargo of that most malignant and pestiferous of all antichristian publications. (p.76)

However, there was a flip side to this zealous advent of modernity. Many of the Hindu households became suspicious of the purpose of these colleges and considered these as hubs of conversion³. It may not be entirely erroneous to take this distrust as one of the first seeds of the reformist/revivalist friction.

It is almost impossible that in a cultural sphere as vibrant as nineteenth century Bengal modernity would remain a unidimensional phenomenon. As it was appreciated and accepted by a certain group, at the same time it was severely questioned by another group and there was yet another section which was trying to create a separate identity with the ideals borrowed from the western agents of modernity.

Sumit Sarkar in his book *Modern India* gives a statistic according to which by 1880 the total number of English Educated Indians were close to fifty thousand (Sarkar 65). English education not only meant the opening of new avenues of knowledge but was also a gateway to an opportunity of prestigious services. This worked as an added incentive for the Bengali *bhadralok* to welcome English education with much warmth. Sarkar goes through painstaking details to explicate how this *bhadralok* was a more complicated notion than both upper-caste and middle class. *Bhadralok* consisted of people belonging to Bramhin, Kayastha and Vaidya alike, and though they took the European model as their immediate ideal, yet the source of their income varied from government service to law, education, medicine instead of trade which was monopolised by their colonial ruler with a few exceptions of Marwari traders.

The *bhadralok* class was looking up to Europe in general and Britain in particular. Hence the immediate model that they had in front of them was that of Victorian England. And the idea that the reformist creed of Bengal renaissance had borrowed some of its ideals from Victorian England may after all have some solid ground for its claim. This is why it became almost an always and already to pronounce the eighteenth-century poetic practice as crude and obscene. On the other hand, there was a necessity to make space for the newer kind of literary practice. The nascent modern cultural sphere felt an urge to craft a literary tradition worthy of their stature, a literary tradition that would suit the taste of the *bhadralok*. Rosinka Chaudhuri in her book *The Literary Thing* gives us a detailed description of how writers such as Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay, Harachunder Basu or Madhusudan Dutta were desperate to create a new tradition and this generation of literary practitioners, more often than not, considered the literary inheritance of the yesteryear as unworthy for the consumption of the newly emerged class. Though many sub genres and their creators⁴ were subject to this critique but Chaudhuri puts special emphasis on Bharat Chandra and the charges of obscenity labelled against his most celebrated works *Annadamangal* and *Bidyasundar*(Chaudhuri 3). Bharat Chandra Ray was the court poet of Raja Krishnachandra Ray of Nadia and can be considered as the single most important representative of his age. His most famous work *Annadamangal* continued to enjoy an unwavering popularity for more than half a century after his death. Perhaps, this popularity also played its part in the war waged against him. It was necessary for likes of Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay or Madhusudan Dutta to create a foil in him in order to make way for a new order. The need to exorcise the ghost of Bhratchandra is well exhibited in a letter written by Madhusudan Dutt:

I see that I have actually done something that ought to give our national poetry a good lift, at any rate, that will teach the future poets of Bengal to write in a strain very different from that of the man of Krishnanagar – the father of a very vile school of poetry...(qtd. in Chaudhuri 5)

Chaudhuri marks this attitude as emblematic of a period which created a binary of high and low culture, which upheld a literary tradition palatable for the newly emerged *bhadralok* class and relegated the traditional to the margin (Chaudhuri 7), though Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay changed this attitude later and emerged as a sympathizer of traditional poetics. In one of his later essays "Lokshiksha", he unequivocally lamented the loss of these traditions which he perceived as important vehicles of mass education, and he held the new English educated class responsible for the demolition of the older order (Chattopadhyay 324).

As Sisir Kumar Das points out, literature always works apropos to the social economical milieu and a shift in the literary style often coincides with the shift in the political 'power' or 'patronage' (Das 17). The predominant literary style in Bengal shifted from an earlier tradition of poetry (*mangalkabya*, *panchali gaan*) to a newer tradition of prose. The prose tradition first germinated in a missionary project of translating the Bible into the vernacular and in writing grammar books for Fort William college. According to Susil Kumar Dey it is the missionary effort that gave rise to a fortified tradition of prose which stood strong against the tide of vile literary practice of eighteenth century. In this respect William Carey and his book *Kathopokathan* requires a special mention. Prose eventually facilitated a number of significant changes that were to alter the course of Bengali intellectual practice. The most important amongst these was the newspaper. A number of newspapers and periodicals from *Dikdarshan*⁵ to *Tatwabodhini* were being published and became absolutely indispensable in forming the opinion of the new public sphere.

Though prose emerged as the preferred genre of the city dwelling intellectuals, but it would be wrong to keep poetry or drama outside this orbit. As has been discussed earlier, Madhusudan Dutt and Rangalal Bandopadhyay were tirelessly engaged in creating a new tradition of poetic practice. Their position was more complex than it seemed from outside. Both Dutt and Bandyopadhyay exhibited loyalty towards western education but at the same time there was a need to preserve the legacy of the indigenous poetry. This is more appropriate about Rangalal Bandyopadhyay than Madhusudan Dutt. Rangalal Bandyopadhyay in his *Bangla Sahitya Bishoyok Prostab* (1852) defended Bharatchandra Ray Gunakar and few other poets against the raging debate on obscenity. While considerable work has been done on Madhusudan Dutt and his poetic endeavour, Rangalal Bandopadhyay has remained a minor poet of the canon. Like many of his contemporaries Rangalal too was well versed in both western and Indian literature. Hence when he felt the urge to create a new tradition he wanted to bridge both the worlds. Most of the stories of Rangalal's long verses were derived from Colonel Todd's *Annals and Antiquities of Rajasthan* and he also chose freely from his experience of reading English verses. Many of later historians such as Asit Kumar Bandopadhyay have critiqued his attempt to fit Indian contents in western schemata.

Rangalal Bandyopadhyay and his generation saw colonial modernity as a boon (both in material and spiritual sense) which instilled a novelty in the society burdened with old beliefs and helped the cultural sphere to reach a perceived point of maturity. Perceiving modernity as a boon was not peculiar to the generation who had a firsthand experience of it. Eminent historians of Bengali literature continued to carry this attitude well into the last decades of the twentieth century. When critics are continuously questioning the validity of Bengal renaissance and its scope, literary historian Bhudeb Chaudhuri does not have any problem in perceiving Bengal renaissance as an agent of emancipation from the "medieval" way of life (Bhudeb Chaudhuri 183). And according to him the vitality that modernity brought for the weak and cocooned Bengali race was individuality. In Chaudhuri's analysis individuality helped the emerging *bhadralok* class to get rid of a social system which was by and large ritualistic (Bhudeb Chaudhuri 194). Chaudhuri takes Derozio, Rammohan and Bidyasagar as three most representative faces of Bengal renaissance and argues that it is their strong sense of individuality that enabled both Rammohan and Bidyasagar to fight for social reforms and it is the strong sense of individuality that would be later moulded into a stronger nationalistic impulse.

The scope of Bengal renaissance has been put to question. It has long been marked as a phenomenon for a niche population. The same can be said of the modernity that followed the renaissance. Though Calcutta was a centre of civilization, a greater number of people still dwelled in villages. Modernity possibly meant nothing but an extravagance for the people who continued to perish at the margins due to various ill-planned schemes introduced by the colonial Government. Hence the much celebrated and debated modernity was actually confined within a close circle of city-bred *Babus*, meaning almost nothing for the rest of the vast population. And once the first waves of mass hysteria over the modernity was beginning to wane, the darker sides of colonial modernity were becoming more and more visible.

As has already been mentioned that modernity was neither a uni-dimensional idea nor it enjoyed an uninterrupted period of blind worship. Some of the overzealous activities undertaken by missionary priests had already kindled a suspicious attitude towards the education system which was predominantly manned by European scholars. Hindu households increasingly withdrew their wards from Hindu College. If this was the general anxiety expressed by general people, then there was also a parallel scholarly anxiety expressed by some of the greatest scholars of the day. The leading name in this list would be Dinesh Chandra Sen. Rosinka Chaudhuri described Dinesh Chandra as an 'organicist' scholar who raised his voice against the contamination of the Bengali minds. In spite of being a devout reader of western literature, Dinesh Chandra perceived modernity as a ravage which has put the past into an irretrievable position. For him a self-conscious Bengali identity was impossible without a strong connection to the roots. Dinesh Chandra Sen's complaint against the new generation was their complete amnesia of the older world and their overindulgence in English poetics. Dinesh Chandra makes it clear that he certainly does not belong to this league. Rosinka Chaudhuri shows how Dinesh Chandra distanced himself from this group he criticised through a clever use of pronoun. He directs his attack towards those ardent followers of English metres who have no respect towards *payar*⁶ or those who have preferred Juliet or Andromache to Behula or Lahana. Rosinka Chaudhuri believes that Dinesh Chandra's inclination towards the traditional was a strategy to counter the series of changes that were occurring around him (Chaudhuri lviii).

Apart from the material domain, the spiritual reaction towards modernity came in the garb of religious/social reform movements. Rammohan Roy was not a direct student of Henry Derozio but the rational agnosticism on one hand and the increasingly narrow ritualistic constitution of Hinduism drove him towards a new avenue. Though he continuously published manifestos of his religious ideology but the formation of first *Atmiya Sabha* and finally *Bramho Samaj* in 1828 was the culmination of his attempt to usher in a religious reform. Rammohan Roy was not alive to see the fortification of *Bramho Samaj* but he had already initiated a particular way of interpreting religious texts which formed much of the trajectory of *Bramho Samaj* for the rest of the century. There is a common notion that *Bramho Samaj* had borrowed some of its ideologies from Christianity⁷ to counter the narrow practices of mainstream Hinduism but it did not share a particularly happy relationship with Christianity either. Many of the *Bramho* stalwarts including Rammohan and Debendranath vehemently opposed the project of mass conversion undertaken by Alexander Duff. Debendranath in particular was agitated by the manifold activities of Missionaries. While Rammohan's emphasis was more spiritual and his approach was more social reform oriented, Debendranath Tagore felt the necessity to posit *Bramho Samaj* as an alternative for Christianity. To counter the increasing magnetic attraction of Christianity Debendranath started a religious school *Tatwabodhini Pathshala* to teach science, religion, philosophy and significantly enough the medium was Bengali. Debendranath even went to the extent of personally requesting the elite households for not sending their children to the missionary schools (Chattopadhyay 131). Though these social reformers drew their first inspiration from the education disseminated by the missionaries it took them little or almost no time to identify the missionaries as their rivals. Was Debendranath's attempt to establish an alternative religious school a simple attempt of social reform? Or was it a strategy to create a new order in a society that was in an inchoate situation? The debate might go on, but Debendranath's rebellion was not a stray incident but was one of the first among many. The religious modernity initiated by *Bramho Samaj* was eventually replaced by a political modernity and Kanailal Chattopadhyay sees Surendranath Bandyopadhyay's immense popularity with the young Bengali people as emblematic of that change.⁸ The complexity of Hindu reaction to the modernity too, was a complex phenomenon. Hinduism had received a considerable blow from the colonial modernity and the reforms that followed it but it maintained a silent presence and it is needless to say that in the large area of rural Bengal, Hinduism was still enjoying its undisputed authority. However, from the second half of nineteenth century there was a considerable movement towards reviving Hinduism. Nabagopal Mitra's initiative to start *Hindu Mela* in 1867 was a rudimentary form of an attempt to assemble Hindu people for a nationalist cause. This attempt was certainly meeting with some success since it influenced very differing

personalities like Shashadhar Tarkachuramani and Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay alike. Bhabatosh Dutta in his *Chintanayak Bankim Chandra* argues that to equate Bankim Chandra with the likes of Shashadhar Tarkachuramani would be an injustice to his dynamism as a true representative of Bengali middle class and their intellectual participation in the complex process of modernity (Dutta 14). But at the same time, one cannot deny that Bankim Chandra indeed showed a strong Hindu inclination in some of his fiction and nonfiction writing. One of the primary characteristics and perhaps the most known is a deep distrust of the racial other. The Hindu nationalist did not try to challenge his colonial master, but the reflected fury was transferred on the two hundred years long interim Muslim rule. Bankim Chandra's *Anandamath* and *Rajsingha* are two texts which upheld an idealist Hindu warrior culture against the brutal Muslim ruler. In *Rajsingha* Bankim Chandra encashes on the much-misinterpreted myth of Aurangzeb's brutality. *Anandamath*, on the other hand, portrays local Muslim ruler as the ultimate enemy. And in his essay 'Bangalar itihaz Sambandhe Kayekti Katha' he goes a step further when he attacks Minhaz Uddin for writing an imaginary history and chastises it as 'upokotha'. Readers find Minhaz Uddin at the receiving end of caustic abusive words – *khauritachikur* (a person with shaven head), *gohatyakari*⁹ (a person who slays cow) from Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay who laments that generations of Indologists had written their histories depending on these hearsays (Chattopadhyay 290). However unfortunate this otherization was, it was indeed a result of the colonial modernity. A self-conscious nationalist 'self' needed to create the 'other' which could represent everything that the 'self' resented.

Influenced by the high ideals of European modernity nineteenth century Bengal witnessed the rise of a multifaceted modernity. It would not be wrong to claim that there were many modernity(s) simultaneously present and continuously jostling to make their presence felt. Though colonial intervention is often held responsible for ushering in this seismic shift in the political and cultural sphere of the nineteenth century Bengal, but it is also true that the colonized people gradually started to carve out modernity according to their own convenience. Thus, colonial modernity provided colonized *bhadralok* with a space where they could exercise a rebellion (even if it is against an older order) which certainly gave them a sense of control (however limited in nature) over one's own self. But the trajectory of modernity was never monolithic in nature. A simultaneous existence of the many modernity(s) made the nineteenth century Bengal a dynamic cultural space yielding a varied result. And in spite of functioning in a closed society with limited success, it left its strong impression on the nascent nation and in a certain sense paved the way for its successful emergence.

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References:

- 1 In between the time of Robert May and Felix Carey there were missionaries as well as civil servants who helped in this dissemination. Joshua Marshman, Hyde Eyst, William Carey worked hard to bring success to this mission. Rammohan was influenced by some of these missionaries.
- 2 These were primary schools where the medium of instruction was Sanskrit, and the curriculums often followed traditional scriptural knowledge.
- 3 Alexander Duff indeed converted a young student called Surendranath and his eleven years old wife into Christianity and became hugely unpopular with the common Bengali people.
- 4 Dashrathi Ray faced a similar though a much smaller scale attack from English educated reader. It was also true that audience gave way to reader as the new century approached.
- 5 *Dikdarshan* has been considered by many as the first journal published in Bengali and *Tatwabodhini* was a journal edited and published by Debendranath Tagore to discuss the true form of *BramhoSamaj* and its scope.
- 6 *Payar* is a metre that was popular in seventeenth and eighteenth century Bengal.
- 7 Rabindranath Tagore showed this closeness through a beautiful imagery in his novel *Gora*. Sucharita, a girl brought up in a Brahmo household always keeps a picture of Christ in her room.
- 8 *Bramho Samaj* was suffering from a crisis of leadership and National Congress was established in 1885.
- 9 Both the terms were commonly used to abuse Muslim people.

